

Performance Recognition and Employee Output of Pharmaceutical Manufacturing Firms in Enugu State, Nigeria

¹Ezeh, C. J. PhD; ²Onah, S. PhD; and ³Ugochukwu, L. N. PhD

Department of Business Administration, Enugu state University of Science and Technology

Department of Business Administration, Institute of Management and Technology, Enugu

Accepted: July 14th, 2022

Published: July 31st, 2022

Citations - APA

Ezeh, C. J., Onah, S., & Ugochukwu, L. N. (2022). Performance Recognition and Employee Output of Pharmaceutical Manufacturing Firms in Enugu State, Nigeria. *Contemporary Journal of Management*, 4(4), 20-38

The study evaluated the Performance Recognition and Employee Output of Pharmaceutical Manufacturing Firms in Enugu state, Nigeria. The specific objectives were to; examine the relationship between desirable awards and employee quality of work; the relationship between peer recognition and productivity and the relationship between immediate gratification and employee efficiency of Pharmaceutical Manufacturing Firms in Enugu state, Nigeria. The area of the study comprised of staff of T.U Woods Pharmaceuticals, MICHELLE LABORATORIES, and Juhel pharmaceuticals in Enugu State. The study used the descriptive survey design approach. The primary source of data was the administration of questionnaire. A total population of 1530 staff was used. The adequate sample size of 307, using Freund and William's statistic formula at 5 percent margin of error. 238 staff returned the questionnaire and accurately filled. Data was presented and analyzed by mean score and standard deviation using Sprint Likert Scale and hypotheses were analyzed using Pearson correlation coefficient (r) statistics tool. The findings observed positive significant relationship between desirable awards and employee quality of work ($r = .221 < .865$); positive significant relationship between peer recognition and productivity ($r = .729 < .868$) and there was positive significant between immediate gratification and employee efficiency of Pharmaceutical Manufacturing Firms in South-East, Nigeria, ($r = .364 < .809$). The study concluded that Performance Recognition and Employee Output of Pharmaceutical Manufacturing Firms. The recommended among others that the pharmaceutical firms should like the manufacturing firms get effective reward system that would improve the performance of their staff.

←
ABSTRACT

Keywords: Employee Output; Performance Recognition; Productivity; Pharmaceutical Manufacturing Firms

Introduction

The firms with the winning edge in a competitive work environment are those with the best-trained and talented employees. Employees who are not sufficiently motivated will not perform well (Nikos, 2018). This is why workplace employee appreciation must be ingrained in the culture of every company. Employee appreciation is when a company's employees are recognized for their outstanding performance. Employee recognition in the workplace essentially serves to encourage certain behaviors, practices, or actions that lead to improved performance and beneficial business outcomes. Employees that are happy are more productive. Being acknowledged makes your employees feel like they've mastered their jobs and that they're a good match for their roles and the organization. Employee recognition in the workplace has the potential to be the cornerstone of fostering a culture of self-improvement. One of the most effective methods to recognize employees is to provide them opportunity to develop and improve their skills. To take it a step further, incentivizing learning rewarding individuals who have invested time in self-improvement – would be fantastic (Nikos, 2018).

Organizations utilize recognition as one of the most effective and efficient reward mechanisms to inspire employees. Employee recognition is critical for motivating and enhancing performance. A winning strategic incentive system also includes elements of recognition and gratitude. Recognition is one of the most potent motivators, and it is vital because individuals need to know not just how successfully they have accomplished their goals, but also that their efforts are valued (Orajaka, 2021). Employee appreciation is critical to overall employee success. If the organization does not take it seriously, undesirable consequences may result (Ondhowe, Kadima, and Juma, 2021).

Employee recognition is the timely, informal or official acknowledgment of a person's or a team's conduct, effort, or business outcome that promotes the organization's aims and values and goes above and beyond customary expectations. To be totally effective in the workplace at any level, you must first grasp the psychology of thanking others for their hard work, then use the concepts of employee recognition yourself, and urge others to do the same (Kim, 2020).

Statement of the Problem

Employees not only desire adequate extrinsic remuneration for their job, but they also want to be complimented and valued for their efforts, and firms with motivating systems that include employee recognition have greater staff morale and performance levels. Job discontent arising from low intrinsic and extrinsic motives plagues the majority of Nigeria's industrial industry. Employees who are recognized are more invested in the organization's concerns and perform better.

Employee productivity and performance are both dependent on employee performance. As a result, it is critical for management to guarantee that all efforts and resources are focused on ensuring that human resources reach their maximum potential. Lack of desirable award-Desirable rewards tend to be fair and satisfy different employees' diverging needs; lack of peer recognition linked to employee turnover and poor employee retention; and delayed gratification associated with the refusal or overcoming the temptation to give in to a smaller but more immediate reward in order to receive a larger or more enduring reward later were the issues facing performance recognition and employee output in the study. All businesses are concerned with what should be done to maintain high levels of human resource performance, which includes how best to encourage workers through incentives, rewards, and leadership.

Recognition is an important motivator for every employee's success. This is because job happiness is created when job success is accompanied with rewards that are appreciated and viewed as fair. This will likely enhance incentive to work more in the future to obtain high achievement. Employees interpret acknowledgment as a kind of gratitude and a sense of worth, which promotes morale. Organizational productivity improves as a result of this. Employee recognition is as much an issue of organizational management as it is one of basic human needs. Despite its growing popularity in sociology and organizational psychology circles, this complicated concept remains rather hazy in the management world. Employee recognition is as much an issue of organizational management as it is one of basic human needs.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study was to evaluate the Performance Recognition and Employee Output of Pharmaceutical Manufacturing Firms in Enugu state, Nigeria. The specific objectives were to;

- i. Examine the relationship between desirable awards and employee quality of work of Pharmaceutical Manufacturing Firms in Enugu state, Nigeria.
- ii. Evaluate the relationship between peer recognition and productivity of Pharmaceutical Manufacturing Firms in Enugu state, Nigeria
- iii. Determine the relationship between immediate gratification and employee efficiency of Pharmaceutical Manufacturing Firms in Enugu state, Nigeria

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study;

- i. What is the relationship between desirable awards and employee quality of work of Pharmaceutical Manufacturing Firms in Enugu state, Nigeria?
- ii. What is the relationship between peer recognition and productivity of Pharmaceutical Manufacturing Firms in Enugu state, Nigeria?
- iii. What is the relationship between immediate gratification and employee efficiency of Pharmaceutical Manufacturing Firms in Enugu state, Nigeria?

Statement of the Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses guided the study

- i. There is no positive significant relationship between desirable awards and employee quality of work of Pharmaceutical Manufacturing Firms in Enugu state, Nigeria.
- ii. There is no positive significant peer recognition and productivity of Pharmaceutical Manufacturing Firms in Enugu state, Nigeria
- iii. There is no positive significant immediate gratification and employee efficiency of Pharmaceutical Manufacturing Firms in Enugu state, Nigeria

Significance of the Study

The study will be significant to the following groups;

Employees: Employee recognition shows that their employer recognizes them and their efforts to the team's and company's success. This is especially important when companies expand and evolve. It helps employees feel secure in their worth to the organization, which motivates them to keep doing exceptional job.

Organization: The study is critical for organizations because it helps them stay focused on ways to increase employee engagement and hence enhance overall performance. Even the best employees sometimes struggle to perform successfully owing to a lack of drive.

Researcher/Student: The study is important for researchers and academics who are conducting empirical analysis. It would be valuable to other organizations and scholars who would refer to it and objectively assess the offered proposal.

Review of the Related Literature

Conceptual Framework

Performance

Performance might be simply described as the achievement of quantifiable goals. However, it is not just about what individuals achieve, but also about how they do it. Appropriate conduct and the successful application of needed knowledge, abilities, and competencies result in great performance (Tutorialspoint, 2022). Employee evaluations are used on a regular basis to assist employees recognize their development and feel good about their progress. It also helps them create new goals, which keeps the office buzzing. Employee performance is crucial to the organization's overall success, thus employers need employees who can get the job done (Kimberlee, 2019). Performance is a specific outcome acquired in management, economics, marketing, and other fields that prints characteristics of the organization's competitiveness, efficiency, and effectiveness, as well as its procedural and structural components. The term "performance" refers to an organization's fulfillment of its objectives. It covers outcomes gained or achieved as a result of individual or team contributions to the organization's strategic goals (May, 2020).

Recognition

The act of expressing gratitude and acknowledgment for employees' contributions to the company's purpose, mission, and values is known as recognition. Peer-to-peer recognition, manager-led recognition, and leadership-led recognition are all examples of employee acknowledgment. Employees may understand that their firm values them and their contributions to the success of their team and the company as a whole when they get recognition. This is especially important when companies expand and evolve. It helps employees feel secure in their worth to the organization, which motivates them to keep doing exceptional job (Jens, 2013). Employee recognition is a cornerstone of employee engagement, and implementing it optimizes the potential of your teams and company. Employees who are appreciated are more inclined to work hard and stay longer, and they work together to construct a strong culture that generates money and provides a positive customer experience (Walton, 2022). Effective management has historically prioritized employee appreciation. However, as the battle for talent heats up, the methods in which companies demonstrate their worth to their employees are more crucial than ever (Hastwell, 2021).

Performance Recognition

Because employee performance is so important in firms, managers must become increasingly concerned about ways to boost productivity through better employee performance. There must be a fair balance between the employee's contribution to the organization in terms of employee performance and the organization's contribution to the workers in terms of effective performance reward (Ondhowe, Kadima and Juma, 2021). Organizations continue to use recognition programs to recognize employees who reach a targeted level of performance. As more result-driven recognition systems are employed, the perceived effect on employee engagement, motivation, and satisfaction improves. Employees in organizations with a purposeful or imbedded culture of appreciation are more engaged, motivated, and satisfied (Christina, 2022).

Components of Performance Recognition used in the Study

The components of dependent variable of the study include; desirable award; peer recognition; and immediate gratification

Desirable Awards

To deliver anything like a reward or certificate to someone who has earned it is to award. Offering a competitive wage plan may entice some very skilled people to join your team. Having such personnel on your team may give you the impression that everything is running well. To be sure, everyone is working hard, being prompt, disciplined, and most importantly, motivated. However, the same characteristics of those people, as well as their degree of enthusiasm, frequently fade away with time. And the sole cause of this is workplace disengagement (Gallup, 2021). Winning an organization award reflects the devotion and hard effort that workers put into their jobs every day. Recognizing the victory encourages employees to share in the company's success and take pleasure in the environment they've created with their colleagues.

Peer Recognition

Employees publicly appreciate one other's aid, contributions, abilities, talent, or well-done work via peer recognition, also known as peer-to-peer acknowledgment. Peer acknowledgment may take many forms: in a team or corporate chat, during an online or offline meeting, by email, a feedback tool, a micro bonus, a LinkedIn endorsement, and so on. Employee appreciation may take many forms. Peer-to-peer, leader-to-team-member, and employer-to-employee are the three most popular. A typical employee appreciation program is a mix of these (Neelie, 2021). Genuine expressions of praise amongst coworkers are known as peer recognition. Many employee recognition programs provide managers exclusive responsibility and authority for employee recognition (MacLennan, 2021). When members of the same team or department complement each other on their work, this is known as peer recognition. It might be for a job well done or just to encourage each other by providing good feedback at random. Many businesses are beginning to see the value of providing an official avenue for peers to recognize one another, and many are working to include it into their operations (Clarke, 2021).

Immediate Gratification

Immediate gratification is the feeling of being satisfied or receiving a reward as quickly as you respond. Immediate gratification refers to the urge (and subsequent inclination) to sacrifice a future advantage in exchange for a less

gratifying but more immediate benefit (Courtney .and Ackerman, 2022). Delayed gratification is the refusal of instant gratification in the hopes of getting a good and long-lasting benefit in the long run. To put it another way, delayed gratification defines the process in which a person avoids the lure of an immediate benefit in favor of a later reward. In general, delayed gratification refers to deferring a smaller, more immediate pleasure in exchange for a greater, longer-lasting reward later (Carducci, 2019).

Employee

An employee is a person who is employed to work for a person or corporation in exchange for a wage or payment (Lord, I.2021). An employee is someone who works for someone else who decides what has to be done and how it should be done. For the staff to accomplish their jobs, John supplies the store, merchandise, and equipment. His employees are expected to wear uniforms and work according to their schedules. All the person needs to do is arrive at work on time and prepared, and do the tasks as directed (Lord, 2021). An employee is a person recruited by a company to do a certain task (Heathfield, 2021).

Output

The overall production of products and services produced by a country during a specific period is referred to as output. The phrase can refer to all of an individual's, company's, factory's, or machine's work, energy, commodities, or services (Market Business News, 2022). The number of products or services produced by a corporation, industry, or country in a specific time period, whether consumed or utilized for future production, is referred to as output. The output of an economic activity is a product or service that is available for sale or use elsewhere after inputs have been consumed (Wikipedia, 2013). The output metric compares productivity to efficiency. It appears often in ordinary dialogue (Down, 2019).

Employee Output

Employee output (Bárceñas, 2020) is the amount of work completed by an employee during a given period of time. Employee output may be thought of as a measure of a person's efficiency in performing a task. Employees are just as valuable as a company's product or service portfolio, and they have the power to create or ruin a firm. As a result, a corporation should invest in its personnel while simultaneously expecting a return on that investment through the productivity of those people. Employee output is a measure of an individual's or a group's productivity. It is assessed by examining the entire workforce or employee production over a period of time. In most circumstances, an individual's productivity will be measured against the average production of other employees doing comparable work. Employee productivity is important because the amount of money spent on employee compensation should be less than what the employee earns for the firm via his job (Jill, 2019)

Components of Employee Output that was used in the Study

The components of employee output used in the study include; employee quality of work; productivity; employee efficiency

Employee Quality of Work

The favorableness or unfavourability of a work environment for employees in a company is referred to as quality of work (Chand, 2018). Employee work quality is linked to a set of goals, organizational circumstances, and procedures, as well as employees' feelings of being safe, fulfilled, and able to grow and develop as people (Teryima, Faajir and Emakwu, 2016). Some successful businesses attribute their success to providing their workers with an excellent quality of life at work. Executive managers have recognized the necessity to create a work environment that stimulates people to perform better in order to increase their firms' productivity. The role of an organizational employee, the architecture of their workspace, and what they require to manufacture goods or deliver services more successfully are all factors in the quality of their work (Ahmad, 2015).

Productivity

Employee productivity indicates how productive and efficient the organization's staff is. They make good use of their working hours to get more and better outcomes in less time. Focusing on the appropriate things at the right times is the key to increasing workforce productivity. To increase workplace productivity, companies must first understand what is going on inside their teams and then solve those issues (Dave, 2022). Productivity is a measure of the efficiency with which commodities or services are produced.

Employee Efficiency

Employee efficiency is a trait that refers to an employee's speed and accuracy when doing a particular assignment. Employee productivity is the principle; the more efficient they are, the more productive they will be if properly managed. The profitability of many businesses is under threat. As a result, it's critical that staff perform the proper jobs in the right way. More may be generated with the same quantity of input by working effectively (Bronwyn 2018). Every company compensates its employees for their dedication and effectiveness. Individuals must meet their given goals within the specified time range. Employees must adhere to strict deadlines and produce results on time. Employees must complete their task on schedule in order to receive timely feedback and recognition from both management and external clients (Prachi, 2021).

Conceptual Framework of the Study

Source: Researcher's Field Compilation, 2022

Theoretical Review

The investigation was guided by two theories: Adam Equity theory and Vroom's expectation theory. However, the study was based on Adam Equity Theory, which requires a fair balance between an employee's inputs. According to equity theory, one's inputs and outputs are compared to the inputs and outcomes of others. Inequity can arise as a result of receiving less or more results than relevant people.

Adams Equity Theory

In 1963, American psychologist John Stacey Adams established the Adams Equity Theory. According to equity theory, an individual's motivation is influenced by their impression of being treated fairly in relation to others (Miner, 1980). Even an individual's inputs and outputs are not equal, according to equity theory. Inputs Outcomes Education, intellect, experience, and training are all valuable assets. Pay, internal incentives, and fulfilling oversight Skills, seniority, age, gender, and ethnicity Perks of seniority, fringe benefits, and employment status social standing, work effort, personal attractiveness, health, and features of the spouse (Pritchard, 1969). The individual's inputs, such as productivity and/or job quality, may grow or decline. Education and skill level are more easily changed, while sex, ethnicity, and ethnic origin are not.

The study was founded on this idea, which also supported the study's first objective. Employees strive for parity between the inputs they provide to a job and the outputs they receive, as compared to the perceived inputs and outcomes of others. The equity hypothesis of John Stacey Adams explains why wages and conditions alone don't influence motivation. It also explains why rewarding one individual with a raise or promotion might demotivate others. The Adams Equity Theory explains why a person's motivation is not determined just by their compensation and perks. It explains why a raise or promotion seldom achieves the anticipated result. It has the potential to demotivate other personnel. Being treated fairly and equitably is really important to employees.

Vroom's Expectancy Theory

In 1964, Victor H. Vroom Theory was created. This theory describes motivation as an individual-controlled mechanism that governs decisions among many sorts of voluntary activity. According to expectancy theory, an individual will behave or act in a given manner because they are driven to choose one activity over others because of the expected outcome of that conduct (Oliver, 1974). In essence, the attractiveness of the outcome determines the incentive for behavior selection. However, the cognitive process through which an individual analyzes many motivating variables is at the heart of the idea. This is done before making a final decision. The outcome is not the only element to consider while deciding how to behave (Oliver, 1974).

Empirical Review

The Relationship between Desirable Awards and Employee Quality of Work of Pharmaceutical Manufacturing Firms in South-East, Nigeria

Emakwu, Teryima, and Faajir (2016) A research of Nigeria Breweries Plc in Lagos looked at employee quality of work life as a driver of management success in commercial enterprises. The research's goal was to investigate the effects of employee Quality of Work Life (QWL) as a factor of management efficiency in business organizations, with Nigerian Breweries plc, Lagos as the case study. The study's data was mostly gathered from primary and secondary sources. Multiple regression analysis was used to examine the data. The findings suggest that various problematic elements are impacting Nigerian Breweries Plc's achievement of Quality of Work Life (QWL). The study found that the company uses numerous ways to increase quality of work life (QWL) and management performance.

Antecedents of quality of work life orientation: An empirical inquiry in the Malaysian public sector organization was investigated by Ahmad and Che-Ha (2016). The goal of the study was to see how social capital and leadership behavior affected the quality of work-life balance in Malaysian government agencies. 500 Malaysian public sector entities filled out survey questionnaires. The study used a quantitative approach. The findings reveal that leadership behavior has a similar impact in both the public and private sectors. According to the findings, relational conduct is more common than task-oriented behavior.

In the manufacturing business in South-South Nigeria, Agbaeze and Ebirim (2020) did research on the reward system and organizational performance. The study's goals were to determine the relationship between market rate analysis and organizational commitment in manufacturing firms in South-South Nigeria, investigate the relationship between financial rewards and organizational performance in manufacturing firms in South-South Nigeria, and investigate the relationship between non-financial rewards and employee performance in the manufacturing industry in South-South Nigeria. The data was collected using a survey study methodology and primary data by giving a series of questionnaires to 257 management staff from chosen manufacturing enterprises in Rivers, Delta, and Bayelsa States, respectively. The results suggest that the incentive structure has a considerable impact on organizational performance. Simple linear regression, Pearson product moment correlation coefficient, and the chi-square technique were used to evaluate the hypotheses.

The Relationship between Peer Recognition and Productivity of Pharmaceutical Manufacturing Firms in South-East, Nigeria

Making Employee Recognition a Tool for Achieving Improved Performance: Implications for Ghanaian Universities was the subject of a research by Abena and Kyeremeh (2016). The study's goal was to learn about the many forms of employee recognition programs and their advantages, as well as to investigate the nature of employee recognition in Ghanaian institutions and make recommendations to university administrators on how to enhance employee recognition. The study used a survey research approach. The findings suggest that formal, informal, and day-to-day employee recognition can drive employees in Ghanaian institutions to achieve high levels of performance.

Timoti (2020) did a review of the literature on Motivation and Employee Productivity. The research was conducted in Zimbabwe. The study's goal was to perform a literature analysis and look at ideas and empirical data on the link between employee motivation and organizational productivity, with the goal of figuring out how motivational theories may be used to boost productivity. Primary and secondary data were used in the investigation. The findings suggest that numerous ideas and approaches may be utilized to motivate employees, which has an influence on productivity. According to the findings, it is vital to emphasize that optimizing financial and non-financial benefits is critical in motivating employees.

The Determinants of Employee Productivity in Listed Manufacturing Firms in Southwestern Nigeria was investigated by Omoneye, Omotola, and Olugbenga (2021). The goal of the study was to determine the degree of staff productivity and the factors that influence it in listed manufacturing enterprises in southern Nigeria. For this investigation, a descriptive survey design was used. A basic random sampling procedure was used to pick a sample of 394 respondents. The descriptive and inferential statistics were used to examine the data acquired through a structured questionnaire. The majority of respondents had ordinary production levels, according to the research. Management and organizational variables were shown to have the highest impact on staff productivity, followed by

organizational/technical factors, production and finance factors, and finally production and finance factors. Financial, management, personal, and organizational variables all have a substantial and negative impact on worker productivity, according to the findings.

The Relationship between Immediate Gratification and Employee Efficiency of Pharmaceutical Manufacturing Firms in South-East, Nigeria

The Mitigating Effect of Employee Engagement on Work Alienation, Port Harcourt, Nigeria: A Literature Review was undertaken by Miebaka and Ofurum (2021). The study's goal was to look at the ideas and aspects of employee involvement, as well as work alienation, its effects, and how employee enlightenment affects work alienation. The study used a survey research approach. The findings suggest that the employees under investigation are either unaware of their feelings of work alienation or, more likely, are overly invested in their jobs. Employees are considered to have an easy time finding passion for their meaningful work, as well as a high level of satisfaction and motivation.

Employee Engagement and Its Relationship to Organizational Performance and Sustainability was investigated by Mboga and Troiani (2018). The study's goal was to look at the impact of several factors on employee engagement among customer service personnel across a variety of industries in the United States. Organizations that do not develop and engage their staff risk losing important talent to competitors. A sample of 262 participants from customer service sectors such as transportation, banking, athletics, childcare, insurance, hospitality, information technology, and administrative assistants from Northern New Jersey and Philadelphia, Pennsylvania were surveyed using a Likert scale survey with statistical analysis. The findings suggest that work environment, relationship management, employee engagement, and career development were among the aspects investigated to analyze the impact on worker engagement.

A review of employee engagement: Empirical research was undertaken by Hasan, Nikmah, Nurbaya, Fiernaningsih, and Wahyu (2021). From Khan, who specializes on the state of human psychology, the research intended to examine the function of employee engagement as a topic of human resource management. The research employed qualitative approaches. The results revealed that the engagement topic study has increased. The study indicated that human resource management in a company requires a high level of flexibility in terms of individual rights, as well as employee participation in organizational operations. According to the survey, firms will have high employee engagement if communication and relationships between employers and employees are well-managed, resulting in a good view.

Methodology

The area of the study comprised of staff of T.U Woods Pharmaceutical Industry Ltd, 11 T.U Woods Avenue Ibagwa Nike Enugu, Uguwaji Rd, Enugu; Michelle Laboratories Limited, 23/2 Thinkers Corner, Enugu; Juhel 35 NKWUBOR ROAD, Emene in Enugu State. These organizations were selected due their proximity, number of staff and above capital base of 10 million Naira. The study used the descriptive survey design approach. The primary source of data was the administration of questionnaire. A total population of 1530 staff was used. The adequate sample size of 307, using Freund and William's statistic formula at 5 percent margin of error. 238 staff returned the questionnaire and accurately filled. That gave 76 percent response rate. The validity of the instrument was tested using content analysis and the result was good. The reliability was tested using the Pearson correlation coefficient (r). It gave a reliability co-efficient of 0.71 which was also good. Data was presented and analyzed by mean score (3.0 and above agreed while below 3.0 disagreed) and standard deviation using Sprint Likert Scale. The hypotheses were analyzed using Pearson correlation coefficient (r) statistics tool.

Data presentation and analyses

The Relationship between Desirable Awards and Employee Quality of Work of Pharmaceutical Manufacturing Firms in South-East, Nigeria

Table 1: Responses on the Relationship between Desirable Awards and Employee Quality of Work of Pharmaceutical Manufacturing Firms in South-East, Nigeria

		5	4	3	2	1	ΣFX	-	SD	Decision
		SA	A	N	DA	SD		X		
1	The employee awards make them feel valued and motivate them to work harder.	580	296	36	20	26	958	4.03	1.504	Agree
		116	74	12	10	26	238			
		48.7	31.1	5.0	4.2	10.9	100%			
2	Awards make the employee aware that good work will be rewarded and it promotes their willingness to work.	715	112	18	52	35	932	3.92	1.506	Agree
		143	28	6	26	35	238			
		60.1	11.8	2.5	10.9	14.7	100%			
3	The wards staff members aware of outstanding accomplishments and boost their moral for high productivity.	465	312	18	52	35	882	3.71	1.378	Agree
		93	78	6	26	35	238			
		39.1	32.8	2.5	10.9	14.7	100%			
4	Award of additional fee for performance exceeding satisfactory pushes employees to put in all their energy to work.	735	104	18	52	33	942	3.96	1.588	Agree
		147	26	6	26	33	238			
		61.8	10.9	2.5	10.9	13.9	100%			
5	Desirable award build improves relationships with the employees and flows of communication.	258	512	18	52	21	861	3.62	1.221	Agree
		57	128	6	26	21	238			
		23.9	53.8	2.5	10.9	8.8	100%			
Total Grand mean and standard deviation								3.694	1.439	
									4	

Source: Field Survey, 2022

Table 1, 190 respondents out of 238 representing 79.8 percent agreed that the employee awards make them feel valued and motivate them to work harder 4.03 and standard deviation of 1.504. Awards make the employee aware that good work will be rewarded and it promotes their willingness to work 171 respondents representing 71.9 percent agreed with mean score of 3.92 and standard deviation of 1.506. The wards staff members aware of outstanding accomplishments and boost their moral for high productivity 171 respondents representing 71.9 percent agreed with mean score of 3.71 and standard deviation of 1.378. Award of additional fee for performance exceeding satisfactory pushes employees to put in all their energy to work 173 respondents representing 72.7 percent agreed with mean score of 3.96 and 1.588. Desirable award build improves relationships with the employees and flows of communication 185 respondents representing 77.7 percent agreed with a mean score of 3.62 and standard deviation of 1.221.

The Relationship between Peer Recognition and Productivity of Pharmaceutical Manufacturing Firms in South-East, Nigeria

Table 2: Responses on the Relationship between Peer Recognition and Productivity of Pharmaceutical Manufacturing Firms in South-East, Nigeria

		5 SA	4 A	3 N	2 DA	1 SD	ΣFX	- X	SD	Decision
1	Peer recognition encourages personal connections with their team members.	430 86 36.1	396 99 41.6	18 6 2.5	52 26 10.9	21 21 8.8	917 238 100%	3.85	1.504	Agree
2	Find-remind-bind helps create and strengths relationship and improves output-in the organization	430 86 36.1	396 99 41.6	18 6 2.5	52 26 10.9	21 21 8.8	917 238 100%	3.85	1.506	Agree
3	Employee confidence and self-esteem is enhanced with peer recognition as managers add value to each of the employees	395 79 33.2	424 106 44.5	18 6 2.5	58 26 10.9	21 21 8.8	916 238 100%	3.85	1.378	Agree
4	Employee who receives frequent recognition and appreciates is likely to be productive.	230 46 19.3	600 150 63.0	18 6 2.5	20 10 4.2	26 26 10.9	894 238 100%	3.76	1.588	Agree
5	There is a stronger moral on the recognition of the employee who performs better and others	580 72 30.3	552 106 44.5	36 6 2.5	22 10 4.2	23 44 18.2	1213 238 100%	3.93	1.221	Agree
	Total Grand mean and standard deviation							3.694	1.439 4	

Source: Field Survey, 2022

Table 2, 135 respondents out of 238 representing 77.7 percent agreed that Peer recognition encourages personal connections with their team members 3.85 and standard deviation of 1.504. Find-remind-bind helps create and strengths relationship and improves output-in the organization 135 respondents representing 77.7 percent agreed with mean score of 3.85 and standard deviation of 1.506. Employee confidence and self-esteem is enhanced with peer recognition as managers add value to each of the employees 185 respondents representing 77.7 percent agreed with mean score of 3.85 and standard deviation of 1.378. The owner of the organization makes informed decisions on internet adoption 206 respondents representing 66.6 percent agreed with mean score of 3.74 and 1.588. There is a stronger moral on the recognition of the employee who performs better and others 178 respondents representing 74.8 percent agreed with a mean score of 3.93 and standard deviation 1.221

The Relationship between Immediate Gratification and Employee Efficiency of Pharmaceutical Manufacturing Firms in South-East, Nigeria

Table 3: Responses on the Relationship between Immediate Gratification and Employee Efficiency of Pharmaceutical Manufacturing Firms in South-East, Nigeria

		5 SA	4 A	3 N	2 DA	1 SD	∑FX	- X	SD	Decision
1	The immediate gratification strengthens the mind and shapes the employee character.	715	159	18	20	26	938	3.94	1.504	Agree
		143	53	6	10	26	238			
		60.1	22.3	2.5	4.2	10.9	100%			
2	Immediate gratification builds self-control and will power of the employees to perform their task.	290	552	18	20	26	906	3.81	1.506	Agree
		58	138	6	10	26	238			
		24.4	58.0	2.5	4.2	10.9	100%			
3	The reinforcement of self-discipline through immediate gratification promotes success of the organization	320	576	18	20	14	748	3.98	1.378	Agree
		64	144	6	10	14	238			
		26.9	60.5	2.5	4.2	5.9	100%			
4	Instant gratification extremely motivates and stands to see that their behavior has a result.	835	204	18	20	4	1081	4.54	1.588	Agree
		167	51	6	10	4	238			
		70.2	21.4	2.5	4.2	1.7	100%			
5	Boosting productive can be done with gratification of the employee that add creativity.	665	244	18	48	14	989	4.16	1.221	Agree
		133	61	6	24	14	238			
		55.9	24.6	2.5	10.1	5.9	100%			
Total Grand mean and standard deviation								3.694	1.439	
									4	

Source: Field Survey, 2022

Table 3, 226 respondents out of 238 representing 73.2 percent agreed that the immediate gratification strengthens the mind and shapes the employee character. 3.65 and standard deviation of 1.504. Immediate gratification builds self-control and will power of the employees to perform their task 196 respondents representing 82.4 percent agreed with mean score of 3.81 and standard deviation of 1.506. The reinforcement of self-discipline through immediate gratification promotes success of the organization 208 respondents representing 87.4 percent agreed with mean score of 3.98 and standard deviation of 1.378. Instant gratification extremely motivates and stands to see that their behavior has a result 218 respondents representing 218 percent agreed with mean score of 4.54 and 1.588. Boosting productive can be done with gratification of the employee that add creativity 194 respondents representing 80.5 percent agreed with a mean score of 4.16 and standard deviation 1.221.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis One: There is No Positive Significant Relationship between Desirable Awards and Employee Quality of Work of Pharmaceutical Manufacturing Firms in South-East, Nigeria

Table 4: Correlations

		The employee awards make them feel valued and motivate them to work harder.	Awards make the employee aware that good work will be rewarded and it promotes their willingness to work.	The wards staff members aware of outstanding accomplishments and boost their moral for high productivity .	Award of additional fee for performance exceeding satisfactory pushes employees to put in all their energy to work.	Desirable award build improves relationships with the employees and flows of communication.
The employee awards make them feel valued and motivate them to work harder.	Pearson Correlation	1	.378**	.391**	.221**	.240**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.001	.000
	N	238	238	238	238	238
Awards make the employee aware that good work will be rewarded and it promotes their willingness to work.	Pearson Correlation	.378**	1	.865**	.824**	.650**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000	.000
	N	238	238	238	238	238
The wards staff members aware of outstanding accomplishments and boost their moral for high productivity.	Pearson Correlation	.391**	.865**	1	.817**	.605**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000	.000
	N	238	238	238	238	238
Award of additional fee for performance exceeding satisfactory pushes employees to put in all their energy to work.	Pearson Correlation	.221**	.824**	.817**	1	.703**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.001	.000	.000		.000
	N	238	238	238	238	238
Desirable award build improves relationships with the employees and flows of communication.	Pearson Correlation	.240**	.650**	.605**	.703**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	
	N	238	238	238	238	238

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 4 Showed the Pears on correlation matrix on desirable awards and employee quality of work showing the correlation coefficients, significant values and the number of cases. The correlation coefficient shows .221 <.865. This value indicates that correlation is significant at 0.05 level (2 tailed) and implies that there was positive significant relationship between desirable awards and employee quality of work of Pharmaceutical Manufacturing Firms in South-East, Nigeria (r=. .221 <.865.). The computed correlations coefficient is greater than the table value of r = .000 with at alpha level for a two-tailed test (r=.221 <.865., p <.05).

Decision Rule

The decision rule is to accept the null hypothesis if the computed r is less than the tabulated r otherwise rejects the null hypothesis

Decision

Since the computed (r =.221 <.865.) is greater than the table value of .000, we reject the null hypothesis. Therefore, we concluded that there was positive significant relationship between desirable awards and employee quality of work of Pharmaceutical Manufacturing Firms in South-East, Nigeria as reported in the probability value of (r=.221 <.865., p<.05).

Hypothesis Two: There is No Positive Significant Peer Recognition and Productivity of Pharmaceutical Manufacturing Firms in South-East, Nigeria

Table 5: Correlations

		Peer recognition encourages personal connections with their team members.	Find-remind-bind helps create and strengths relationship and improves output-in the organization	Employee confidence and self-esteem is enhanced with peer recognition as managers add value to each of the employees	Employee who receives frequent recognition and appreciates is likely to be productive.	There is a stronger moral on the recognition of the employee who performs better and others
Peer recognition encourages personal connections with their team members.	Pearson Correlation	1	.842**	.729**	.811**	.765**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	280	280	280	280	280
Find-remind-bind helps create and strengths relationship and improves output-in the organization	Pearson Correlation	.842**	1	.770**	.785**	.846**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000	.000
	N	280	280	280	280	280
Employee confidence and self-esteem is enhanced with peer recognition as managers add	Pearson Correlation	.729**	.770**	1	.868**	.754**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000	.000
	N	280	280	280	280	280

value to each of the employees						
Employee who receives frequent recognition and appreciates is likely to be productive.	Pearson Correlation	.811**	.785**	.868**	1	.844**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000		.000
	N	280	280	280	280	280
There is a stronger moral on the recognition of the employee who performs better and others	Pearson Correlation	.765**	.846**	.754**	.844**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	
	N	280	280	280	280	280
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).						

Table 5 Showed the Pearson correlation matrix on **peer recognition and productivity** showing the correlation coefficients, significant values and the number of cases. The correlation coefficient shows $.729 < .868$. This value indicates that correlation is significant at 0.05 level (2 tailed) and implies that there was positive significant relationship between **peer recognition and productivity of Pharmaceutical Manufacturing Firms in South-East, Nigeria** ($r = .729 < .868$). The computed correlations coefficient is greater than the table value of $r = .000$ with at alpha level for a two-tailed test ($r = .729 < .868, p < .05$).

Decision Rule

The decision rule is to accept the null hypothesis if the computed r is less than the tabulated r otherwise rejects the null hypothesis.

Decision

Since the computed ($r = .729 < .868$) is greater than the table value of $.000$, we reject the null hypothesis. Therefore, we concluded that there was positive significant relationship between **peer recognition and productivity of Pharmaceutical Manufacturing Firms in South-East, Nigeria** as reported in the probability value of ($r = .729 < .868, p > .05$).

Hypothesis Three: There is No Positive Significant Immediate Gratification and Employee Efficiency of Pharmaceutical Manufacturing Firms in South-East, Nigeria

Table 6: Correlations

		The immediate gratification strengthens the mind and shapes the employee character.	Immediate gratification builds self-control and will power of the employees to perform their task.	The reinforcement of self-discipline through immediate gratification promotes success of the organization	Instant gratification extremely motivates and stands to see that their behavior has a result.	Boosting productive can be done with gratification of the employee that add creativity.
The immediate gratification strengthens the mind and shapes the employee character.	Pearson Correlation	1	.809**	.719**	.576**	.364**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	280	280	280	280	280
Immediate gratification builds self-control and will power of the employees to perform their task.	Pearson Correlation	.809**	1	.703**	.515**	.463**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000	.000
	N	280	280	280	280	280
The reinforcement of self-discipline through immediate gratification promotes success of the organization	Pearson Correlation	.719**	.703**	1	.712**	.444**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000	.000
	N	280	280	280	280	280
Instant gratification extremely motivates and stands to see that their behavior has a result.	Pearson Correlation	.576**	.515**	.712**	1	.431**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000		.000
	N	280	280	280	280	280
Boosting productive can be done with gratification of the employee that add creativity.	Pearson Correlation	.364**	.463**	.444**	.431**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	
	N	280	280	280	280	280

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 6 Showed the Pearson correlation matrix on **immediate gratification and employee efficiency** showing the correlation coefficients, significant values and the number of cases. The correlation coefficient shows .364 <.809. This value indicates that correlation is significant at 0.05 level (2 tailed) and implies that there was positive significant relationship between immediate gratification and employee efficiency of Pharmaceutical Manufacturing Firms in South-East, Nigeria (r= .364 <.809). The computed correlations coefficient is greater than the table value of r = .000 with at alpha level for a two-tailed test (r= .364 <.809, p<.05).

Decision Rule

The decision rule is to accept the null hypothesis if the computed r is less than the tabulated r otherwise rejects the null hypothesis.

Decision

Since the computed ($r = .364 < .809$) is greater than the table value of $.000$, we reject the null hypothesis. Therefore, we concluded that there was positive significant relationship between immediate gratification and employee efficiency of Pharmaceutical Manufacturing Firms in South-East, Nigeria as reported in the probability value of ($r = .364 < .809$, $p < .05$).

Discussion of Findings

The Relationship between Desirable Awards and Employee Quality of Work of Pharmaceutical Manufacturing Firms in South-East, Nigeria

The calculated ($r = .221.865$) is larger than the table value of $.000$, implying a positive significant link between desirable rewards and employee quality of work of Pharmaceutical Manufacturing Firms in South-East, Nigeria, as given in the probability value of ($r = .221.865$, $p < .05$). Teryima, Faajir, and Emakwu (2016) examined employee quality of work life as a factor of management efficiency in business organizations: a case study of Nigeria Breweries Plc in Lagos to support their findings. The study found that the company uses numerous ways to increase quality of work life (QWL) and management performance. In the manufacturing business in South-South Nigeria, Agbaeze and Ebirim (2020) did research on the reward system and organizational performance. The results suggest that the incentive structure has a considerable impact on organizational performance.

The Relationship between Peer Recognition and Productivity of Pharmaceutical Manufacturing Firms in South-East, Nigeria

The calculated ($r = .729.868$) is larger than the table value of $.000$, implying that there was a positive significant link between peer recognition and productivity of Pharmaceutical Manufacturing Firms in the South-East of Nigeria, as stated in the probability value of ($r = .729.868$, $p > .05$). Abena and Kyeremeh (2016) conducted a study on Making Employee Recognition a Tool for Achieving Improved Performance: Implications for Ghanaian Universities in support of the findings. The findings suggest that formal, informal, and day-to-day employee recognition can drive employees in Ghanaian institutions to achieve high levels of performance. Timoti (2020) did a review of the literature on Motivation and Employee Productivity. The research was conducted in Zimbabwe. According to the findings, it is vital to emphasize that optimizing financial and non-financial benefits is critical in motivating employees.

The relationship between immediate gratification and employee efficiency of Pharmaceutical Manufacturing Firms in South-East, Nigeria

The calculated ($r = .364.809$) was larger than the table value of $.000$, implying a positive significant link between rapid gratification and staff efficiency of Pharmaceutical Manufacturing Firms in South-East, Nigeria, as reflected in the probability value of ($r = .364.809$, $p = .05$). Miebaka and Ofurum (2021) did a study on The Mitigating Effect of Employee Engagement on Work Alienation, Port Harcourt, Nigeria: A Literature Review to back up their findings. The findings suggest that the employees under investigation are either unaware of their feelings of work alienation or, more likely, are overly invested in their jobs. Employees are considered to have an easy time finding passion for their meaningful work, as well as a high level of satisfaction and motivation. A review of employee engagement: Empirical research was undertaken by Hasan, Nikmah, Nurbaya, Fiernaningsih, and Wahyu (2021). From Khan, who specializes on the state of human psychology, the research intended to examine the function of employee engagement as a topic of human resource management. The research employed qualitative approaches. The results revealed that the engagement topic study has increased. The study indicated that human resource management in a company requires a high level of flexibility in terms of individual rights, as well as employee participation in organizational operations.

Summary of the Findings

- i. There was positive significant relationship between desirable awards and employee quality of work of Pharmaceutical Manufacturing Firms in South-East, Nigeria, ($r = .221 < .865$.)
- ii. There was positive significant peer recognition and productivity of Pharmaceutical Manufacturing Firms in South-East, Nigeria, ($r = .729 < .868$).
- iii. There was positive significant immediate gratification and employee efficiency of Pharmaceutical Manufacturing Firms in South-East, Nigeria, ($r = .364 < .809$)

Conclusion

Desirable prizes, peer recognition, and instant satisfaction showed a positive significant link with employee quality of work, productivity, and staff efficiency of Pharmaceutical Manufacturing Firms in South-East Nigeria, according to the study. Organizations utilize recognition as one of the most effective and efficient reward mechanisms to inspire employees. Employee recognition is critical for motivating and enhancing performance. A winning strategic incentive system also includes elements of recognition and gratitude. Recognition is one of the most potent motivators, and it is vital because individuals need to know not just how successfully they have accomplished their goals, but also that their efforts are valued (Orajaka, 2021).

Recommendation

The following were suggested by the study:

- i. pharmaceutical companies, like industrial companies, should have an efficient compensation system in place to boost employee performance.
- ii. Management should see peer recognition as a critical project rather than one of the most costly and ineffective practices that makes no meaningful contributions to the business.
- iii. Organizations should strive for high levels of immediate gratification in order to successfully express serious connections between management and employees for a job well done.

References

- Abena, S. A. and Kyeremeh, D. K. (2016). Making employee recognition a tool for achieving improved performance: Implication for Ghanaian Universities. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 7(34); 1-7.
- Agbaeze, K. E. and Ebirim, O. C. (2020). Reward system and organizational performance in the manufacturing industry in South-South Nigeria. *International Journal of Management, Social Sciences, Peace and Conflict Studies*, 3(4); 241-254.
- Ahmad, S. (2015). *Human Resource Management: In practice*: First Edition; New Delhi: Tilak Wasan Discovery Publishing House PVT Ltd.
- Bárceñas, M. (2020). *Employee productivity: The Ultimate Guide*. Retrieved from <https://fellow.app/blog/management/employee-productivity-the-ultimate-guide-for-managers/>.
- Bronwyn, W. (2018). *What is employee efficiency?* Retrieved from <https://www.effactory.com/knowledge/what-is-employee-efficiency>.
- Cambridge Dictionary (2017). *Meaning of "award" in the English Dictionary*. Retrieved from Cambridge University Press. Retrieved 21 May 2017.
- Carducci, B. J. (2019). *Basic Processes of Mischel's Cognitive-Affective Perspective: Delay of Gratification and Conditions of Behavioral Consistency*. The Psychology of Personality: Viewpoints, Research, and Applications. John Wiley and Sons. pp. 443-4.
- Chand, S. (2018). *Quality of Work Life: it's Meaning and Definition | Employee Management*. Retrieved from <https://www.yourarticlelibrary.com/employee-management/quality-of-work-life-its-meaning-and-definition-employee-management/26112>
- Christina, Z. (2022). *How your company can make performance recognition work*. Retrieved from <https://www.itagroup.com/insights/how-your-company-can-make-performance-recognition-work>.
- Clarke, L. (2021). *Why peer recognition is important in high performing teams*. Retrieved from <https://inside.6q.io/peer-recognition-important-performing-teams/>
- Courtney E. and Ackerman, MA. (2022). *What is Instant Gratification? A Definition + 16 Examples and Quotes*. Retrieved from <https://positivepsychology.com/instant-gratification/#:~:text=Instant>
- Cropanzano, R. (Ed.) (1993). *Justice in the workplace: Approaching fairness in human resource management*. Hillsdale: Academic Press, Inc.
- Adams, J. S. (1965). *Inequity in social exchange*. In L. Berkowitz (Ed.), *advances in experimental psychology* pp. 267-299. New York: Academic Press.
- Dave, N. (2022). *How to increase employee productivity: the only guide you'll ever need*. Retrieved from <https://blog.hubstaff.com/employee-productivity/>.
- Down, T. (2019). *How to measure employee productivity*. Retrieved from <https://www.breathehr.com/en-gb/blog/topic/employee-performance/how-to-measure-employee-productivity>.
- Gallup, P. (2021). *Creative employee award titles: Explained with types and examples*. Retrieved from <https://blog.vantagecircle.com/employee-award-titles/>.
- Hasan, H., Nikmah, F., Nurbaya, S., Fiernaningsih, N. and Wahyu, E. (2021). A review of employee engagement: Empirical studies. *Management Science Letters*, 11(7), 1969-1978.
- Hastwell, C. (2021). *Creating a culture of recognition*. Retrieved from <https://www.greatplacetowork.com/resources/blog/creating-a-culture-of-recognition>.
- Heathfield, S.M. (2021). *What, exactly, is an employee?* Retrieved from <https://www.thebalancecareers.com/what-is-an-employee-1918111>.
- Indeed Editorial Team (2021). *Peer recognition: definition and ideas for recognizing your peers*. Retrieved from <https://www.indeed.com/career-advice/career-development/peer-recognition>.
- Indeed Editorial Team (2021). *What is quality working? Definition, importance and tips*. Retrieved from <https://www.indeed.com/career-advice/career-development/quality-working>.
- Indeed Editorial Team (2021). *Employee recognition: Definition and its importance*. Retrieved from <https://www.indeed.com/career-advice/career-development/why-recognition-is-important>
- Jens, B. (2013). *Three concepts of recognition*. Retrieved from <https://www.cambridge.org/core/journals/international-theory/article/abs/three-concepts-of-recognition>.
- Jill, H. (2019). *The importance of employee productivity*. Retrieved from <https://bizfluent.com/info-8292773-importance-employee-productivity.html>.

- Kim, H. (2020). *Employee recognition is important: Here's how to do it well*. Retrieved from <https://cuttingedgepr.com/employee-recognition-important/>
- Kimberlee, L. (2019). *Importance of employee performance in business organizations*. Retrieved from <https://smallbusiness.chron.com/importance-employee-performance-business-organizations-1967.html>.
- Lord, I. (2021). *What is an employee?* Retrieved from <https://study.com/academy/lesson/what-is-an-employee-definition-types.html>.
- MacLennan, C. (2021). *What is peer recognition and 13 reasons why you should care*. Retrieved from <https://www.motivosity.com/blog/13-reasons-to-have-a-peer-recognition-program/>.
- Market Business News (2022). *What is output? Definition and meaning*. Retrieved from <https://marketbusinessnews.com/financial-glossary/output-definition-meaning/>.
- May, H. (2020). *What is performance?* Retrieved from <https://thecelebtimes.com/what-is-performance-according-to-different-authors>.
- Mboga, J. and Troiani, K. (2018). An empirical study: Employee engagement and linkage to organization performance and sustainability. *International Journal of Business & Applied Sciences*, 7(2); 42-56.
- Miebaka, D. T. and Ofurum, C. R. (2021). The mitigating effect of employee engagement on work alienation, Port Harcourt, Nigeria: A Literature Review. *Academic Scholars Publishing League (ASPL) International Journal of Management Sciences*,9(1);93-107.
- Miner, J. B. (1981). *Theories of organizational motivation*. In G. W. England, R.
- Montana, P. J. and Charnov, B. H (2008). *Management – 4th edition*; Barron's Educational Series, Inc.
- Murray,J. (2020). *What is an employee?* Retrieved from <https://www.thebalancesmb.com/what-is-the-definition-of-an-employee-398246>.
- Neelie, V. (2021). *Peer recognition in the workplace: the what, why and how*. Retrieved from <https://www.aihr.com/blog/peer-recognition>.
- Nikos, A. (2018). *Employee recognition in the workplace: the why and how*. Retrieved from <https://www.efrontlearning.com/blog/2018/04/employee-recognition-workplace-benefits-ways.html>
- Oliver, R. (1974). Expectancy theory predictions of salesmen's performance. *Journal of Marketing Research* 11(3), 243-253.
- Omoneye, O. O., Omotola O. O. and Olugbenga, A. O. (2021). Determinants of employee productivity in listed manufacturing firms in Southwestern Nigeria. *International Journal of Applied Management and Technology*, 20(1);194–210.
- Ondhowe, F. A., Kadima, J. M., & Juma, D. (2021). Influence of recognition practice on employee performance at Lake Victoria South Water Services Board in Kisumu, Kenya. *The Strategic Journal of Business & Change Management*, 8 (1), 650 – 661.
- Orajaka, U. P. (2021). Organizational performance and its effects to employee recognition and job satisfaction in some selected Public Universities in the South East, Nigeria. *Asian Journal of Economics, Business and Accounting*, 21(3): 97-106.
- Prachi J. (2021). *Workplace efficiency - being efficient at workplace*. Retrieved from <https://www.managementstudyguide.com/workplace-efficiency.htm>.
- Pritchard, R. D. (1969). Equity theory: A review and critique. *Organizational Behavior and Human Performance*, 4, 176-211.
- Teryima, S. J., Faajir, A. and Emakwu, J. (2016). Examining employee quality of work life as a determinant of managerial effectiveness in business organizations: A study of Nigeria Breweries Plc, Lagos. *Global Journal of Human Resource Management*,4(5);1-24.
- Timoti, K. (2020). *Motivation & employee productivity: A review of literature*. Great Zimbabwe University, Zimbabwe Department of Human Resources Management. Retrieved from file:///C:/Users/JUDION/Downloads/MotivationEmployeeProductivityAReviewOfLiterature.pdf.
- Tutorialspoint (2022). *What is performance?* Retrieved from https://www.tutorialspoint.com/performance_management/performance_management_understanding.htm#:~:text=Performance.
- Walton, S. (2022). *Employee recognition: What it is, why it matters, and how to use it effectively*. Retrieved from <https://www.quantumworkplace.com/employee-recognition>.
- Wikipedia (2013). *Output*. Retrieved from [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Output_\(economics\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Output_(economics))